

1 Microbial assessment of foaming dynamics in full-scale WWTP anaerobic digesters

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9 Abstract

10 Research on foaming processes in wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) anaerobic
11 digesters is increasing since it is a common phenomenon that can seriously affect
12 digesters performance and treatment cost. This paper presents data from a full-scale
13 experience of foam monitoring and antifoam reagents dosing as well as microbial
14 community structure. The association of foaming episodes with microbial population
15 structure and operational parameters has improved understanding of foaming episodes
16 and their causes. During this long-term study (273 days), two foaming episodes occurred
17 in the anaerobic digesters under study. Microbial community analysis showed that the
18 first foaming episode is correlated with the proliferation of *ST-12K33 (midas_s_22)*,
19 which could be related to variations in the hydraulic retention time, a decrease in inflow
20 solids concentration, and a decrease in digesters total alkalinity. The second foaming
21 episode coincide with a clear migration of *Ca. Microthrix parvicella* from the activated
22 sludge (bulking episodes) to the anaerobic digesters and its capacity to metabolize
23 substrate under anaerobic conditions. Laboratory experiments showed that an increase in
24 anaerobic digestion temperature and sludge pre-treatments have a positive impact on

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25 foam biodegradability and, therefore, they could be used as foam mitigation strategies.
26 Finally, a techno-economic analysis showed that foaming episodes had an over cost of
27 about 250 € d⁻¹ and dropped the WWTP energy self-sufficiency from 67 to 63%.

28 **Keywords**

29 Anaerobic digestion, WWTP, bulking, foaming, pre-treatments

30

31 **1. INTRODUCTION**

32 Foaming events are a critical and a recurrent problem in municipal wastewater treatment
33 plants (WWTPs) anaerobic digesters (AD) (Sch et al., 2016). Foaming leads to multiple
34 operational problems, including inefficient gas transfer from the liquid to the gas phase,
35 blockage of biogas or sludge pipes, and security issues (Alfaro et al., 2014; Jiang et al.,
36 2021a; Moeller et al., 2015; Pagilla et al., 1997). Furthermore, foaming can cause an
37 inverted solids profile in the digesters, with higher solids concentration at the top,
38 resulting in dead zones that reduce the active volume. These phenomena can lead to
39 uneven stabilised sludge and lower biogas yields (Ganidi et al., 2009). In addition to the
40 operational problems and safety hazards, foaming events result in economic losses due to
41 the reduced biogas production, manpower overtimes, and cleaning expenses (Ganidi et
42 al., 2009; Jiang et al., 2021a; Pagilla et al., 1997; Westlund et al., 1998a). Surveys of
43 WWTPs operators have shown that foaming events are frequent and seasonal in anaerobic
44 digestion process (Kougias et al., 2014; Lindorfer and Demmig, 2016; Moeller et al.,
45 2012; Rodríguez-Roda et al., 2012). Characterizing foaming mechanisms and developing
46 early warning and foaming control methods is thus critically important (Yang et al.,
47 2021).

48 Foaming in AD has been associated with several factors, such as organic overloading,
49 accumulation of volatile fatty acids (VFAs), inadequate mixing, temperature fluctuations,
50 and the presence of extracellular polymeric and hydrophobic substances (Yang et al.,
51 2022, 2021). However, foaming in AD has also been related to the proliferation of
52 filamentous bacteria in the activated sludge system such as *Gordonia* (formerly
53 *Nocardia*) and *Ca. Microthrix* (Lienen et al., 2014; Rodríguez-Roda et al., 2012;
54 Westlund et al., 1998b). An overgrowth of filamentous bacteria in the activated sludge
55 system can result in an increased abundance in the WWTP AD, due to the feeding of
56 thickened waste activated sludge (WAS) to digesters (Pagilla et al., 1997; Sch et al., 2016;
57 Westlund et al., 1998b). Hence, these microorganisms could be the responsible of
58 foaming episodes in both the activated sludge and in anaerobic digesters (Ganidi et al.,
59 2009, Jiang et al., 2021). For example, Lienen et al. (2014) reported that mesophilic
60 anaerobic co-digester fed with WAS rich in *Ca. Microthrix parvicella* are prone to foam
61 formation, particularly if the digesters are co-loaded with fat, oil and grease (FOG).

62 Overgrowth of filamentous bacteria in the activated sludge systems has been associated
63 to both wastewater properties (e.g. fats and oils content, temperature, C/N ratio) and
64 operational factors (e.g. cellular retention time, organic loading rate and dissolved
65 oxygen) (Rodríguez-Roda et al., 2012; Wágner et al., 2022; Xie et al., 2007). Filamentous
66 bacteria are characterised by a hydrophobic cell surface and/or the production of
67 biosurfactants that trap gas bubbles, creating a viscous and an stable foam (Pagilla et al.,
68 2002; Westlund et al., 1998b). Some filamentous bacteria transported with the WAS may
69 survive under anaerobic conditions, limiting their decay during AD process (Ganidi et al.,
70 2011). Consequently, a thorough understanding of microbial communities and the
71 microorganisms responsible for foam formation in the activated sludge system is crucial

72 for developing efficient control measures against foaming events in AD (Jiang et al.,
73 2021a).

74 Several methods have been tested to prevent foam formation and foam accumulation in
75 AD. These include better-designed reactors or the use of mechanical stirring instead of
76 pneumatic stirring (Subramanian et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2021). Chemicals such as poly-
77 aluminium chloride, which inhibits lipase enzymatic activity and blocks the substrate
78 uptake by filamentous organisms (Rossetti et al., 2005), zero valent iron (Kong et al.,
79 2019), and antifoam reagents (Suhartini et al., 2019) have also been tested. Modifying the
80 digester operational temperature and implementing thermal pre-treatments have also been
81 used to control foam formation in AD (Ganidi et al., 2009).

82 Soddell and Seviour (1995) showed that most of the filamentous species isolated from
83 foams in activated sludge systems could grow at anaerobic mesophilic (30 - 35 °C)
84 conditions. However, moderate temperature increases from 37 to 41 °C have been
85 reported to control the relative abundance of *Ca. M. parvicella* in full-scale plants (Lienen
86 et al., 2014). It is important to consider that the temperature of the foam is usually lower
87 than the temperature of the liquid phase due to inadequate mixing (Ganidi et al., 2009),
88 making it difficult to control the foam temperature when small temperature increments
89 are applied to full-scale digesters. Thermophilic (50 - 55 °C) conditions have been
90 reported to yield higher destruction of filamentous microorganisms compared to
91 mesophilic conditions (Marneri et al., 2009). A two-phase AD system, combining a
92 thermophilic (55 - 70 °C) fermentation digester and a mesophilic methanogenic digester,
93 could be an option to control foaming, increase biogas yields, and obtain a digestate with
94 a higher dewaterability properties (Romero-Güiza et al., 2021; Subramanian et al., 2015).
95 Thermal pre-treatments have also been reported as an effective method to prevent
96 foaming in AD (Alfaro et al., 2014). Westlund et al. (1998a) reported that heating WAS

97 (with a high content of *Ca. M. parvicella*) at 70 °C for 5 min reduced foam formation,
98 while Barjenbruch and Kopplow (2003) reported that filamentous structures were
99 successfully reduced by heating sewage sludge at 121 °C for 60 min.

100 The aim of this study was to assess the seasonal microbial community composition and
101 its dynamics in a full-scale WWTP anaerobic digesters and their relationship with
102 operational parameters and foaming episodes. Moreover, different operational
103 temperatures, and thermal and thermo-alkaline pre-treatments have been evaluated as
104 mitigation strategies to reduce foam in AD.

105

106 **2. MATERIAL & METHODS**

107 **2.1. WWTP description**

108 The WWTP under study is located in Lleida (northeast of Spain, UTM 489853 m E,
109 4694716 m N). The current treatment capacity of the WWTP is 160,000 population
110 equivalents. The activated sludge reactors configuration is based on a *Bardenpho*
111 (Anoxic/Oxic/Anoxic) process. The reactors are equipped with advanced process control
112 (APCs) system for nitrogen (aeration, internal & external recirculation controls) and
113 phosphorous removal (FeCl₃ dosing and promotion of enhanced biological phosphorous
114 removal, EBPR), despite not having a dedicated anaerobic zone (Palatsi et al., 2021). The
115 primary sludge (PS), collected in the primary clarifiers, is thickened in two thickening
116 settlers (440 m³). The WAS from the activated sludge system is thickened using a
117 flotation system composed of an air sludge-compressor unit (5 m³) and a flotation unit
118 (435 m³). The thickened PS and WAS are mixed (namely, sewage sludge, SS) in a buffer
119 tank (80 m³) and digested in two thermally isolated mesophilic (35 - 40 °C) reactors
120 (4,960 m³). Digesters mixing is performed by pneumatic biogas injection and the

121 digesters temperature is controlled using an external heat exchanger in the recirculation
122 flow. The digested sludge is dewatered using two centrifuges and sent to agricultural
123 applications.

124 The anaerobic digesters are equipped with antifoam agent (Burst® PF 13 T, BASF)
125 dosing pumps connected to an APC module that ensures that the foam level (h_{foam}) in
126 digesters is maintained below a setpoint (SP) of 40 cm and below a safety threshold of 80
127 cm (Figure 1) (Romero-Güiza et al., 2022). Technical characteristics of antifoam agent
128 are summarized in Table 1S (**Supplementary Material**). Digesters are also equipped
129 with an online biogas analyser (CH_4 , CO_2 , O_2 , and H_2S). The digesters also have an APC
130 module that controls the FeCl_3 (40%) dosing pumps to maintain the H_2S concentration in
131 the biogas below a SP of 80 ppm, to protect the combustion heat and power (CHP) unit
132 and boilers of the WWTP. A complete WWTP description and applied operation/control
133 strategies can be found in Palatsi et al., (2021) and Romero-Güiza et al., (2022).

134 **2.2. Sample collection and analysis**

135 Operational data from Lleida WWTPs includes online sensors data and laboratory
136 measurements. Total suspended solids (TSS), total solids (TS), and volatile solids (VS)
137 were measured according to the Standard Methods for the Examination of Water and
138 Wastewater (APHA, 2005). The chemical oxygen demand (COD), total nitrogen (TN),
139 and total phosphorous (TP) were measured after sample digestion (LT200, Hach) with a
140 VIS-RFID spectrophotometer (DR3900, Hach) using commercial kits (LCK, Hach).
141 Respirometer caps (Oxitop System, VWR) were used to determine the 5-day biochemical
142 oxygen demand (BOD_5). pH and alkalinity were measuring using a pH probe (PHC805,
143 Hach) and an automatic titrator (TitraLab AT1000, Hach). Total alkalinity (TA) was
144 measured at a pH value of 4.3 and the intermediate alkalinity (IA) was measured at a pH
145 value of 5.7 (Hill and Jenkins, 1989; Lahav et al., 2002).

146 One-way analysis of variance (one-way ANOVA) was used to determine whether
147 operational parameter or yield present statistically significant differences among the
148 defined periods, with a statistical significance of $\alpha = 0.05$. When the variance analysis
149 indicated significant differences among periods, Turkey's test ($\alpha = 0.05$) for the multiple
150 comparison of means was used to find means that were significantly different from each
151 other (@Statistics Kingdom, 2017).

152 **2.3. Microbial analysis**

153 Biomass samples from the activated sludge and the anaerobic digesters were sampled in
154 2 mL tubes once per week from October 2021 to July 2022. Samples were stored in a
155 freezer at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until further analysis. Activated sludge samples were collected in the
156 aerobic basin (45 samples), and anaerobic digestion samples were collected in the
157 digesters' recirculation (45 samples).

158 DNA extraction, purification and sequencing were carried out by Novogene Co. (UK).
159 DNA was extracted using the FastDNA™ spin kit for soil (MP Biomedicals, USA)
160 following the manufacturer's protocol. The V3-V4 region of the 16S rRNA gene was
161 amplified using universal primers (341F: 5'-CCTAYGGGRBGCASCAG-3'; 806R: 5'-
162 GGACTACNNGGGTATCTAAT-3'). As a quality control measure, DNA concentration
163 and purity were determined by gel electrophoresis on 1% agarose gel, and
164 spectrophotometrically using the NanoDrop ND-1000 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA).
165 Forward and reverse reads were truncated at 250bp to retain sequences with a quality score
166 >30 . Reads with >5 expected errors were discarded. Dereplication, amplicon sequence
167 variants (ASV) inference and chimera removal were run with DADA2 default parameters.
168 Taxonomic assignment of the ASVs was performed using assign Taxonomy function in
169 DADA2 with a minimum bootstrap confidence of 80%, using MiDAS 4.8 database
170 (Dueholm et al., 2022). Microbial species were assigned to known functional guilds (e.g.,

171 nitrifiers, PAO, methanogens) and morphology (i.e., filamentous) based on the main *in*
172 *situ* properties described to occur in the WWTP
173 (<https://www.midasfieldguide.org/guide/search>). Downstream statistical analyses were
174 performed in R studio (R Core Team, 2020) mainly using the following packages:
175 tidyverse v.1.3.2 (Wickham et al., 2019), ampvis2 v.2.7.32 (Andersen et al., 2018), and
176 variancePartition v.1.2.6 (Hoffman and Roussos, 2021). Differences in overall microbial
177 community structure were explored by principal component analysis (PCA), redundancy
178 analysis (RDA) and variance partitioning, where the ASV reads were Hellinger
179 transformed prior to ordination and operational data was z-scored. A mass balance
180 between species in activated sludge and anaerobic sludge was performed to select the
181 growing species as in Jiang et al., (2021b).

182 **2.4.Data availability**

183 Raw sequences have been deposited to the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) under
184 the project number PRJEB62757.

185 **2.5.Assessing the impact of pre-treatments and anaerobic digestion temperature on** 186 **foam anaerobic biodegradability**

187 The effect of AD operational temperature, thermal pre-treatment, and thermo-alkaline
188 pre-treatment on anaerobic biodegradability of activated sludge foam samples was
189 assessed through biomethane potential (BMP) test. The foam samples were collected
190 from the top of the aerobic basins during foaming episodes in the anaerobic digesters.
191 BMP were carried out following Angelidaki et al., (2009) and Holliger et al., (2016)
192 guidelines. Briefly, BMP tests were carried out in 250 mL serum bottles, each bottle
193 contained 110 mL of inoculum and the amount of foam needed to reach an inoculum-to-
194 substrate ratio (ISR) of 2. The inoculum was collected from the AD in the same WWTP.
195 A blank test containing only inoculum was used to correct the background methane

196 production from the inoculum endogenous respiration. No external buffers or trace
197 elements were added. The vials headspace was flushed with 99.9 % N₂ gas, sealed with a
198 septum, and placed in a thermostatic bath set at the target temperature. The serum bottles
199 were mixed by swirling before each sampling event. All BMP tests and blanks were
200 carried out in triplicate.

201 The impact of anaerobic digestion temperature on foam biodegradability was evaluated
202 at 35, 39, and 42 °C without any pre-treatment. Thermal pre-treatments was performed at
203 70 °C for 30 min, while the thermo-alkaline pre-treatment was performed at 60 °C for 60
204 min and 50.6 g_{NaOH} kg⁻¹_{VS} (Chiappero et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2020; Zhen et al., 2017). All
205 pre-treatments were conducted in a 1-L pressurised stainless-steel reactor, heated with a
206 heating tape at fixed temperature. Subsequently, BMP tests were performed at 39 °C to
207 determine the biodegradability of the pre-treated foam samples.

208 The BMP curves were modelled using a first-order kinetic equation (Eq. 1):

$$209 \quad B = B_{\max} \cdot (1 - e^{-k \cdot t}) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

210 where B is the time-dependent cumulative methane production (mL_{CH₄}·g_{VS}⁻¹), B_{\max} is the
211 ultimate methane production (mL_{CH₄}·g_{VS}⁻¹), k is the apparent first-order rate constant (d⁻¹)
212 ¹, and t is the digestion time (d). Parameters were estimated with 95% confidence
213 intervals using non-linear regression as described in Jensen et al. (2011).

214

215 **3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION**

216 **3.1. Full-scale digesters performance and foaming episodes**

217 Table 1 and Figures 1S-2S summarise the main operational parameters of WWTP and
218 AD performance between June 2021 and July 2022. Figure 2 shows the foam layer (h_{foam})
219 and antifoam dosing profile. As described in Materials and Methods section, digester

220 foaming was controlled by an APC module that doses antifoam to keep the h_{foam} below
221 established SP. According to Figure 2 three operation periods were defined:

- 222 • Period 1 (**P1**) between October 1, 2021, and November 18, 2021 (49 days)
223 comprises a first foaming episode, with a mean h_{foam} of 31 ± 7 cm and antifoam
224 dosing of 23 ± 17 kg d⁻¹.
- 225 • Period 2 (**P2**) between November 19, 2021, and March 18, 2022 (120 d)
226 comprises a period without foaming, with a mean h_{foam} of 18 ± 1 cm and antifoam
227 dosing of 0 kg d⁻¹.
- 228 • Period 3 (**P3**) between March 19, 2022, and July 8, 2022 (112 d) comprises a
229 second foaming episode, with a mean h_{foam} of 34 ± 4 cm and antifoam dosing of
230 43 ± 15 kg d⁻¹.

231 Regarding AD performance, there were significant fluctuations in AD operational
232 parameters between periods, including operational temperature (38.0-39.5 °C), total
233 alkalinity (3,203-3,495 mg_{CaCO₃} L⁻¹), IA/TA ratio (0.19-0.21), and concentration of
234 methane (59-60% CH₄) and hydrogen sulphide (10-78 ppm H₂S) in biogas (Table 1 and
235 Figure 2S). Variation in anaerobic digesters inflow parameters such as hydraulic retention
236 time (HRT, 22-26 d) and organic loading rate (OLR, 1.30-1.71 kg_{VS} m⁻³ d⁻¹) can be
237 explained by the amount and composition of the PS and WAS from the WWTP. Despite
238 these variations are small, there was a noticeable impact on AD performance indicators
239 such as organic matter removal (52-58 %, in % VS), and biogas or methane yields (0.39-
240 0.49 Nm³_{biogas} m³_{reactor} d⁻¹ and 0.53-0.57 Nm³CH₄ kg_{VS}⁻¹_{removed}, respectively).

241 **3.2. Microbial population structure and dynamics**

242 Figure 3A shows the average relative abundance of the 25 most abundant genera in the
243 AD samples. Genera that were found also in high abundance in the activated sludge

244 samples are highlighted in red, despite not having a known role in the anaerobic
245 degradation pathway (e.g. *Tetrasphaera*, *Ca. Microthrix*). These genera could be carried
246 along with the WAS, as previously discussed in Jiang et al., (2021a).

247 Among specific genera from the AD, the methanogenic community was dominated by
248 *Methanotrix* (formerly known as *Methanosaeta*), an acetoclastic methanogen (Figure
249 3B). *Methanotrix* is commonly found in mesophilic anaerobic reactors without co-
250 digestion and in AD systems with low levels of volatile fatty acids and ammoniacal
251 nitrogen (Capson-Tojo et al., 2020; Jiang et al., 2021b; Lu et al., 2018). Hydrogenotrophic
252 methanogens (e.g. *Ca. Methanofastidiosum*, *Methanospirillum*, *Methanobrevibacter*)
253 were also present in low relative abundance (<1%, Figure 3B), which is consistent with
254 other WWTPs mesophilic digesters (Jiang et al., 2021b). The AD samples also showed a
255 high diversity of acetogenic syntrophic species belonging to the genera
256 *Syntrophorhabdus*, *Syntrophomonas*, *Smithella*, *Syntrophobacter* and *Ca. Propionivorax*
257 (Figure 3C).

258 Finally, it is observed in Figure 4 that species with known or putative filamentous
259 morphology exhibit strong temporal patterns, being more abundant in periods when
260 foaming events were detected. Some of the genera such as *Ca. Microthrix* (characteristic
261 of activated sludge systems and associated with bulking events, according to Nittami et
262 al., 2020; Rossetti et al., 2005) increased to more than 10% relative read abundance in
263 P3, whereas *Tetrasphaera*, slightly increased from around 4% to 8% relative read
264 abundance at the end of P2. Others such as *Methanotrix*, *Ca. Brevefilum* and the families
265 *ST-12K33* (species *midas_s_22*) have been recently described as potential foam-forming
266 species in AD due to their filamentous morphology (Jiang et al., 2021a) were more
267 abundant in P1 and P2. Some putative hydrolytic and fermenting bacteria also showed
268 strong temporal dynamics (e.g. *Bacteroidetes midas_s_19*, *Sedimentibacter*

269 *midas_s_1214*). However, hydrolytic, and fermenting bacteria are considered
270 functionally redundant, hence a decrease of their relative abundance does not always
271 imply a lower anaerobic process efficiency, in accordance with Table 1.

272 The results of a global PCA (Figure 3S) show that the microbial community structure
273 follows a dynamic pattern in a temporal fashion, meaning that samples taken during the
274 same period show similar species composition and abundance. However, the overall
275 community structure of AD in WWTPs is known to be altered by the presence of species
276 that are fed with WAS (Jiang et al., 2021a). These species are detected using the 16S
277 rRNA gene marker, but a mass balance analysis indicates that they did not grow in the
278 AD. Non-growing AD species, except those with filamentous morphology, were
279 discarded for further analysis. The results of an RDA analysis (Figure 5) revealed that the
280 dynamic patterns of fermentative-hydrolysers, syntrophic acetogens and methanogens
281 communities were influenced by three main operational parameters: HRT, total alkalinity,
282 and temperature. The syntrophic and methanogenic communities exhibited variability
283 over the sampling period, with total alkalinity and digestion temperature emerging as the
284 primary drivers (Figure 5B, 5C). However, variations in both total alkalinity and
285 temperature were of minor magnitude, or occurred during short periods, quickly returning
286 to average values (Figure 2S), which may explain the absence of distinct clusters in the
287 RDA plot for those communities (Figure 5B and 5C). In contrast, the putative
288 fermentative-hydrolyser community showed two clear clusters (Figure 5A) characterised
289 by a higher abundance of species *midas_s_22* (*ST-12K33*) and two species of the genus
290 *Bacteroidetes vadinHA17*, which correlated with periods of higher HRT. These findings
291 align with the laboratory-scale observations of Peces et al., (2021), where decreasing the
292 HRT led to changes in the fermentative-hydrolyser community, while no significant

293 correlation was observed for the methanogenic community, indicating some degree of
294 manipulability of the microbial communities by operational conditions.

295 **3.3.Causes of foaming in the AD**

296 Figure 6A shows the sludge volume index (SVI) and antifoam dosing with the potential
297 foam-forming species relative abundance in the activated sludge samples. There is an
298 evident trend between filamentous growing in the activated sludge reactors and foam
299 appearance in the anaerobic digesters (Figure 6B). However, the microbial community
300 structures and dynamics of potential foam-forming species differ between the activated
301 sludge and AD samples.

302 During the P1 activated sludge bulking episode, a high relative abundance of the
303 undescribed species *midas_s_334* (family *Microtrichaceae*) and several members of the
304 genus *Tetrasphaera*, some of which are known to exhibit variable filamentous
305 morphology (Nittami and Batinovic, 2022), were observed (Figure 6A). Simultaneously,
306 the digesters experienced a foaming episode (Figure 6B). However, the AD samples
307 presented a high relative abundance of *ST-12K33* (*midas_s_22*), reaching up to 14% in
308 P1. *ST-12K33* (*midas_s_22*), identified as a potential foam-forming species in AD (Jiang
309 et al., 2021a). The cumulative relative abundance of *midas_s_334* and *Tetrasphaera* in
310 the AD samples was stable throughout the study (Figure 4), with average values of 1.7%
311 and 4.3%, respectively (Figure 6B). Therefore, the foaming episode in P1 was potentially
312 driven by the high relative abundance of *ST-12K33* (*midas_s_22*) rather than being
313 attributed to the migration of filamentous species typically found in activated sludge. The
314 proliferation of the potential foam-forming *ST-12K33* (*midas_s_22*) was previously
315 correlated with the concentration of ammoniacal nitrogen and TN (Jiang et al., 2021b).
316 Although the nitrogen compounds concentration of the AD was not monitored in this
317 study, the TN concentration of the AD centrate (liquid fraction of the dewatered sludge)

318 remained constant during the entire study at about $800 \text{ mg}_{\text{TN}} \text{ L}^{-1}$ (Figure 5S). This result
319 suggests that, in this study, TN was not the main driving factor of *ST-12K33* high relative
320 abundance. In contrast, the P1 foaming episode could be related to the digesters' HRT
321 and influent sludge solid concentration.

322 Figure 7A shows the heatmap of the explained variance in filamentous dynamics based
323 on available operational parameters. The two main variables that explained the *ST-12K33*
324 (*midas_s_22*) dynamics were the HRT and TS concentration of the influent sludge. The
325 HRT decreased from 30 d to 20 d during P1 (Figure 1S) due to a decrease in WAS solids
326 concentration (Figure 3S). This decrease was caused by a low performance of WAS
327 thickening, which could be attributed to the bulking episode in the activated sludge, thus
328 coinciding both bulking in activated sludge and foaming in AD (Figure 6). The effect of
329 TS content on foaming remains unclear since low solid systems appear to be more likely
330 to experience foaming (Yang et al., 2021). In this regard, the TS of the influent to AD
331 decreased from 50 to $30 \text{ g}_{\text{TS}} \text{ kg}^{-1}$ during P1 (Figure 1S). Other operational parameters as
332 OLR and TA could also have influenced the microbial community dynamics as obtained
333 from RDA (Figure 7B). TA steadily decreased during P1 from 3,500 to $3,000 \text{ mg}_{\text{CaCO}_3} \text{ L}^{-1}$
334 (Figure 5S), while OLR variations were consequence of SS flowrate and TS content
335 fluctuations (Table 1).

336 During P3, high relative abundance of the well-known filamentous bacteria *Ca. M.*
337 *parvicella* and *Ca. M. subdominans* on activated sludge and AD samples were observed
338 (Figure 6B). RDA analysis shows a clear cluster separation directly related to anti-foam
339 dosing (Figure 7B), and less influenced by operational parameters (Figure 7A). Although
340 migrated species potentially do not contribute to the anaerobic digestion process, they
341 could have promoted the P3 foaming episode, as it can be inferred from the linear
342 correlation between the abundance of “migrating” species in the activated sludge and

343 AD samples (Figure 6S). *Ca. Microthrix* is a well-known foam-forming genus abundant
344 in full-scale WWTPs designed for enhanced biological phosphorus removal (EBPR)
345 (Jiang et al., 2021b). Andreasen and Nielsen (2000) and McIlroy et al (20013) confirmed
346 that physiology of *M. parvicella* is very versatile, not a typical PAO, but with a significant
347 activity under anaerobic conditions (lipid uptake and storage). Moreover, some EBPR
348 species as genus *Tetrasphaera* have also been reported as potential foam-forming species
349 (Jiang et al., 2021a). Relative abundance of *Tetrasphaera* genera in the activated sludge
350 was highest in P2 when there were no bulking episodes in activated sludge nor foaming
351 episode in the AD (Figure 6). *Tetrasphaera* species have diverse physiology, including a
352 capability for fermentative by-products and amino acids (Adhikari et al., 2015; Jiang et
353 al., 2021a). The polyphosphate-accumulating organisms (PAO) relative abundance in the
354 AD samples seems to be linked to a combination of higher relative abundance in the
355 activated sludge samples (migration) and increased OLR in AD (Figure 7S).

356 **3.4. Influence of temperature and pre-treatments on foam biodegradability**

357 BMP of foam samples from the activated sludge in P1 and P3 were carried out at different
358 mesophilic temperatures (35, 39, 42 °C) to evaluate the influence of temperature on foam
359 biodegradability. Table 2 summarizes the methane yield and first-order model outputs of
360 the different BMP tests.

361 Table 2 shows that P1_{foam} had a lower methane yield and a slower degradation rate than
362 P3_{foam}, pointing lower anaerobic degradability of *midas_s_334* compared to *Ca. M.*
363 *parvicella*. BMP shows no significant impact on the samples methane yield with
364 temperature, but it did have an impact on the degradation rates (particularly noticeable in
365 P3_{foam}). For both foam samples, the estimated first-order kinetic constant (*k*) increased as
366 the temperature increased. Specifically, the kinetic constant increased from 0.201 (35 °C)
367 to 0.287 (42 °C) d⁻¹ for P1_{foam} (*midas_s_334*) and from 0.187 (35 °C) to 0.499 (42 °C) d⁻¹

368 ¹ for P3_{foam} (*Ca. M. parvicella*). Although *midas_s_334* may have been responsible in the
369 bulking episode on activated sludge system in P1, results from this research suggest that
370 it is not a potential foam-forming species in AD. The effect of temperature over *Ca. M.*
371 *parvicella* agrees with Lienen et al., (2014), who observed that a moderate temperature
372 increase from 37 °C to 41 °C might help to control the *Ca. M. parvicella* relative
373 abundance in full-scale AD.

374 Regarding the pre-treatments, P1_{foam} thermal pre-treatment at 70°C for 30 minutes
375 increased both the methane yield and the kinetic constant compared to control sample
376 (without pre-treatment, 39 °C). The same thermal pre-treatment did not have an impact
377 on the methane yield and kinetic constant of P3_{foam} (Table 2). The thermo-alkaline pre-
378 treatment had a positive significant impact on the methane yields and kinetic constants of
379 both foam samples (Table 2). The thermo-alkaline pre-treatment had a lower impact on
380 P1_{foam} methane yield than the thermal pre-treatment, suggesting that temperature has an
381 important role on its biodegradability and that temperatures of at least 70 °C are needed
382 to substantially increase their methane yield. Contrariwise, the thermo-alkaline pre-
383 treatment had a much higher impact on P3_{foam} than the thermal pre-treatment. P3_{foam} had
384 a high relative abundance of *Ca. M. parvicella*, which is known to have lipid storage
385 granules and a hydrophobic cell surface able to attract lipids, long chain fatty acids, and
386 other non-polar substrates (Rossetti et al., 2005). The use of an alkali could have increased
387 the solubilisation the lipids trapped in the WAS matrix, resulting in a higher methane
388 yield and degradation rate.

389 **3.5 Economical analysis**

390 The operational over-cost of foaming episodes in AD are not easy to calculate as several
391 factors hinder a fair comparison, including seasonal changes on WAS production, sewage
392 sludge composition (PS and WAS contribution), variation in energy and chemicals costs,

393 among others. Despite these limitations, an economic analysis was conducted considering
394 the operational cost of the WWTP associated with reagents consumption, sludge
395 management and energy production in P3 with or without foaming. To provide a fair
396 comparison between both scenarios, the operational costs of P3 without foaming were
397 estimated using P2 performance yields (Table 3). The economic analysis results showed
398 that foaming episodes represents an additional operational cost of 250 € d⁻¹. This
399 additional cost can be divided as follows: 92 € d⁻¹ due to the sludge management cost of
400 increased sludge production and for additional polyelectrolyte used in dewatering, 86 €
401 d⁻¹ due to antifoam consumption, and 72 € d⁻¹ attributed to the decrease in biogas
402 production. It was estimated that foaming decreased biogas production from 2,263 to
403 2,142 Nm³CH₄ d⁻¹, representing a reduction of 478 kWh d⁻¹ in electricity production. This
404 results in an energy consumption increase from the electricity grid and dropped the
405 WWTP energy self-sufficiency from 67 to 63%.

406 4. CONCLUSIONS

407 The correlation of foam episodes with anaerobic digesters microbial population and
408 operational parameters carried out in this research provides a better understanding of
409 foaming. Microbial analysis showed that the foaming episode in P1 could be related with
410 the proliferation of *ST-12K33* (*midas_s_22*) and it was not directly linked with the species
411 migrating from the activated sludge, such as *midas_s_334*. Statistical analysis showed
412 that the higher relative abundance of *ST-12K33* (*midas_s_22*) in P1 could be influenced
413 by a decrease in HRT and a decrease in the influent sludge TS concentration. In contrast,
414 the foaming episode in P3 was linked to a high relative abundance of *Ca. M. parvicella*,
415 which coincided with a bulking episode in the activated sludge basins, caused by the same
416 species. These results suggest that foam-forming species from the activated sludge system
417 were introduced (migrated) to the digesters, where they persisted and caused foaming.

418 Operational temperature and pre-treatments could be used to mitigate, or event prevent,
419 foaming episodes in anaerobic digesters. Batch experiments showed that increasing the
420 operational temperature from 35 to 42 °C had a significant positive impact on foam
421 degradation rate, but not on the methane yields. Thermal pre-treatment at 70 °C for 30
422 min had a significant positive impact on the methane yield of the foam sample collected
423 in P1, but not on the foam sample collected in P3. The thermo-alkaline pre-treatment (60
424 °C - 60 min - 50.6 g_{NaOH} kg⁻¹_{VS}) increased the methane yield and degradation rate of both
425 foam samples, particularly on the activated sludge foam collected in P3, which had a high
426 relative abundance of *Ca. M. parvicella*.

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Table 1. WWTP operational parameters for each period (mean \pm standard deviation)

Parameter	Units	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3
Primary sludge (PS)				
$Q_{(1)}$	$\text{m}^3 \text{d}^{-1}$	$67 \pm 48 \text{ a}$	$81 \pm 66 \text{ b}$	$92 \pm 51 \text{ b}$
TS ₍₁₎	g L^{-1}	$70 \pm 10 \text{ a}$	$59 \pm 16 \text{ b}$	$63 \pm 15 \text{ b}$
VS ₍₁₎	% of TS	$81 \pm 4 \text{ a}$	$84 \pm 5 \text{ b}$	$75 \pm 5 \text{ b}$
Waste activated sludge (WAS)				
$Q_{(2)}$	$\text{m}^3 \text{d}^{-1}$	$127 \pm 39 \text{ a}$	$167 \pm 72 \text{ b}$	$133 \pm 41 \text{ a}$
TS ₍₂₎	g L^{-1}	$34 \pm 6 \text{ a}$	$32 \pm 5 \text{ b}$	$36 \pm 6 \text{ a}$
VS ₍₂₎	% of TS	$78 \pm 1 \text{ a}$	$79 \pm 2 \text{ b}$	$76 \pm 2 \text{ a}$
Anaerobic Digestion				
$Q_{(3)}$	$\text{m}^3 \text{d}^{-1}$	$194 \pm 39 \text{ a}$	$248 \pm 72 \text{ b}$	$226 \pm 41 \text{ c}$
TS ₍₃₎	g L^{-1}	$42 \pm 6 \text{ a}$	$42 \pm 6 \text{ a}$	$43 \pm 7 \text{ a}$
VS ₍₃₎	% of TS	$80 \pm 2 \text{ a}$	$83 \pm 10 \text{ b}$	$76 \pm 3 \text{ c}$
HRT ₍₃₎	d	$26 \pm 7 \text{ a}$	$22 \pm 9 \text{ b}$	$23 \pm 4 \text{ c}$
OLR ₍₃₎	$\text{kgvs m}^{-3} \text{d}^{-1}$	$1.30 \pm 0.33 \text{ a}$	$1.71 \pm 0.54 \text{ b}$	$1.48 \pm 0.35 \text{ c}$
Temperature ₍₃₎	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	$39.2 \pm 1.3 \text{ a}$	$39.5 \pm 1.4 \text{ a}$	$38.0 \pm 2.7 \text{ b}$
TA ₍₃₎	$\text{mgCaCO}_3 \text{L}^{-1}$	$3,203 \pm 294 \text{ a}$	$3,373 \pm 400 \text{ b}$	$3,495 \pm 368 \text{ c}$
IA/TA ₍₃₎	-	$0.21 \pm 0.01 \text{ a}$	$0.20 \pm 0.01 \text{ b}$	$0.19 \pm 0.02 \text{ c}$
Biogas flow ₍₃₎	$\text{Nm}^3_{\text{biogas}} \text{d}^{-1}$	$3,280 \pm 441 \text{ a}$	$4,041 \pm 772 \text{ b}$	$3,597 \pm 599 \text{ c}$
CH ₄₍₃₎	%	$59 \pm 1 \text{ a}$	$60 \pm 1 \text{ b}$	$59 \pm 3 \text{ a}$
H ₂ S ₍₃₎	ppm	$10 \pm 6 \text{ a}$	$62 \pm 44 \text{ b}$	$78 \pm 40 \text{ c}$
FeCl ₃₍₃₎	kg d^{-1}	$0 \pm 0 \text{ a}$	$100 \pm 20 \text{ a}$	$125 \pm 25 \text{ a}$
h _{foam}	cm	$31 \pm 7 \text{ a}$	$18 \pm 6 \text{ b}$	$34 \pm 4 \text{ c}$
Antifoam dosing ₍₃₎	kg d^{-1}	$23 \pm 17 \text{ a}$	$1 \pm 1 \text{ b}$	$43 \pm 15 \text{ c}$
VS _{removal(3)}	%	$58 \pm 6 \text{ a}$	$58 \pm 6 \text{ b}$	$52 \pm 8 \text{ a}$
Methane yield ₍₃₎	$\text{Nm}^3_{\text{CH}_4} \text{kgvs fed}^{-1}$	$0.30 \pm 0.05 \text{ a}$	$0.29 \pm 0.04 \text{ a}$	$0.29 \pm 0.04 \text{ a}$
	$\text{Nm}^3_{\text{CH}_4} \text{kgvs removed}^{-1}$	$0.54 \pm 0.13 \text{ a}$	$0.53 \pm 0.17 \text{ b}$	$0.57 \pm 0.14 \text{ c}$
	$\text{Nm}^3_{\text{CH}_4} \text{mss fed}^{-3}$	$9.90 \pm 0.09 \text{ a}$	$9.74 \pm 0.10 \text{ b}$	$9.41 \pm 0.48 \text{ c}$
AD yield ₍₃₎	$\text{Nm}^3_{\text{biogas}} \text{m}^3_{\text{reactor}} \text{d}^{-1}$	$0.39 \pm 0.05 \text{ a}$	$0.49 \pm 0.09 \text{ b}$	$0.43 \pm 0.07 \text{ c}$
Sludge Dewatering				
Influent TS ₍₄₎	g L^{-1}	$22.61 \pm 1.51 \text{ a}$	$20.91 \pm 1.73 \text{ b}$	$23.50 \pm 1.26 \text{ c}$
VS ₍₄₎	% of TS	$62 \pm 3 \text{ a}$	$67 \pm 2 \text{ b}$	$63 \pm 1 \text{ a}$
$Q_{(5)}$	ton d^{-1}	$24.09 \pm 8.55 \text{ a}$	$26.43 \pm 10.04 \text{ b}$	$24.05 \pm 8.66 \text{ c}$
Effluent TS ₍₅₎	%	$21.45 \pm 0.88 \text{ a}$	$19.76 \pm 1.27 \text{ b}$	$23.43 \pm 0.84 \text{ c}$
Polyelectrolyte dosing ₍₅₎	$\text{kg kgTS}^{-1} \text{d}^{-1}$	$17.44 \pm 0.35 \text{ a}$	$19.02 \pm 0.38 \text{ a}$	$19.45 \pm 0.39 \text{ a}$

* Numbers in the subscript parentheses are defined according to Figure 1.

** Different lower-case letters in rows indicate statistically significant differences by Turkey's test among periods P1 to P3 ($\alpha=0.05$).

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Table 2. Influence of temperature, thermal and thermo-alkaline pre-treatment on foam biodegradability.

Foam Sample	Pre-treatment	T (°C)	BMP (NL_{CH4} gvs⁻¹)	B_{max} (NL_{CH4} gvs⁻¹)	k (d⁻¹)
P1 _{foam}	-	35	0.103±0.017	0.097±0.007	0.201±0.082
	-	39	0.111±0.020	0.107±0.004	0.277±0.025
	-	42	0.129±0.002	0.117±0.011	0.287±0.001
	70 °C – 30 min	39	0.175±0.020	0.172±0.010	0.309±0.001
	60 °C – 60 min + NaOH	39	0.133±0.026	0.124±0.010	0.374±0.001
P3 _{foam}	-	35	0.200±0.008	0.190±0.010	0.187±0.001
	-	39	0.209±0.024	0.193±0.014	0.321±0.002
	-	42	0.203±0.054	0.197±0.011	0.499±0.002
	70 °C – 30 min	39	0.213±0.030	0.203±0.007	0.330±0.031
	60 °C – 60 min + NaOH	39	0.238±0.032	0.221±0.014	0.456±0.044

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Table 3. Economic analysis for foam episode

Concept	Units	Control	Foam Period
Operational Parameters			
Digester Fed			
Flow [A] ¹	m ³ ·d ⁻¹	226	226
TS [B] ¹	kgTS·d ⁻¹	9685	9685
VS [C] ¹	kgVS·d ⁻¹	7361	7361
Digester Operation and performance			
V _{digester} [D] ¹	m ³	4960	4960
HRT [E=D/A]	d	22	22
OLR [F=C/D]	kgVS·m ⁻³ ·d ⁻¹	1.48	1.48
VS _{Removal} [G] ²	%	58	52
T ²	°C	38	38
CH ₄ [H] ²	% _{CH4}	59.5	59.5
Antifoam [I] ²	kg·d ⁻¹	0	43
Yield [J] ²	Nm ³ CH ₄ ·kgVS _{Elim} ⁻¹	0.53	0.57
Methane [K=J*C*G]	Nm ³ CH ₄ ·d ⁻¹	2263	2142
Biogas [L=K/H]	Nm ³ Biogas·d ⁻¹	3800	3597
Methane energy equivalent [M] ¹	kWh·Nm ⁻³ CH ₄	9.9	9.9
Total Energy Produced [N=M*K]	kWh·d ⁻¹	22401	21204
CHP Power yield [O] ¹	%	40	40
Sludge Dewatering			
Flow [P=B-(C*(1-G/100))]	kgTS·d ⁻¹	5416	5894
TS [Q] ¹	%	23.43	23.43
Coagulant doses ratio [R] ¹	kg _{coagulant} ·kgTS ⁻¹	19.45	19.45
Coagulant flow [S=R*P]	kg _{coagulant} ·d ⁻¹	105.3	115
Energy OPEX			
Energy Requirement [T] ¹	kWh·d ⁻¹	13369	13369
Energy Production [U=N*O]	kWh·d ⁻¹	8960	8482
Energy price [V] ³	€·kWh ⁻¹	0.15	0.15
Energy self-sufficiency [W=(U/T)*100]	%	67	63
Energy Production [X=N*O]	kWh·d ⁻¹	8960	8482
Energy saving [Y=V*U]	€·d ⁻¹	1344	1272
Energy over-cost [Z=X_{control}-X_{foam}]	€·d ⁻¹		72
Reagent OPEX			
Antifoam price [AA] ³	€ kg ⁻¹	4	4
Antifoam cost [AB=AA*I]	€ d ⁻¹	0	86
Antifoam over-cost [AC=AB_{control}-AB_{foam}]	€·d ⁻¹		86
Sludge OPEX			
Sludge production [AD=P/Q]	kg d ⁻¹	23120	25160
Sludge management price [AE] ³	€ kg ⁻¹	0.03	0.03
Sludge management cost [AF=AD*AE]	€ d ⁻¹	693	755
Coagulant price [AG] ³	€ kg _{coagulant} ⁻¹	3.3	3.3
Coagulant cost [AH=AG*S]	€ d ⁻¹	347.6	378
Sludge management cost [AI=AF+AH]	€ d ⁻¹	1041	1133
Sludge management over-cost [AJ=AI_{control}-AI_{foam}]	€·d ⁻¹		92
ECONOMIC BALANCE			
Total OPEX [AK]=[AB]+[AI]	€ y ⁻¹	1041	1219
Total OVER COST [AL=Z+AC+AJ]			250

¹Basis for calculation²Mean values for periods Control (P2) or Foaming (P3)³Estimated according to WWTP OPEX data